

THE 57-TH SMARANDACHE'S PROBLEM II *

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Abstract For any positive integer n , let r be the positive integer such that: the set $\{1, 2, \dots, r\}$ can be partitioned into n classes such that no class contains integers x, y, z with $x^y = z$. In this paper, we use the elementary methods to give a sharp lower bound estimate for r .

Keywords: Smarandache-type multiplicative functions; Mangoldt function; Hybrid mean value.

§1. Introduction

For any positive integer n , let r be a positive integer such that: the set $\{1, 2, \dots, r\}$ can be partitioned into n classes such that no class contains integers x, y, z with $x^y = z$. In [1], Schur asks us to find the maximum r . About this problem, Liu Hongyan [2] obtained that $r \geq n^{m+1}$, where m is any integer with $m \leq n + 1$.

In this paper, we use the elementary methods to improve Liu Hongyan's result. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. *For sufficiently large integer n , let r be a positive integer such that: the set $\{1, 2, \dots, r\}$ can be partitioned into n classes such that no class contains integers x, y, z with $x^y = z$. Then we have*

$$r \geq (n^{n!} + 2)^{n^{n!}+1} - 1.$$

*This work is supported by the N.S.F.(60472068) and the P.N.S.F. of P.R.China.

§2. Proof of the Theorem

In this section, we complete the proof of the theorem.

Let $r = (n^{n!} + 2)^{n^{n!}+1} - 1$ and partition the set $\{1, 2, \dots, (n^{n!} + 2)^{n^{n!}+1} - 1\}$ into n classes as follows:

$$\text{Class 1: } 1, \quad n^{n!} + 1, \quad n^{n!} + 2, \quad \dots, \quad (n^{n!} + 2)^{n^{n!}+1} - 1.$$

$$\text{Class 2: } 2, \quad n + 1, \quad n + 2, \quad \dots, \quad n^2.$$

⋮

$$\text{Class } k: \quad k, \quad n^{(k-1)!} + 1, \quad n^{(k-1)!} + 2, \quad \dots, \quad n^{k!}.$$

⋮

$$\text{Class } n: \quad n, \quad n^{(n-1)!} + 1, \quad n^{(n-1)!} + 2, \quad \dots, \quad n^{n!}.$$

It is obvious that Class k ($k \geq 2$) contains no integers x, y, z with $x^y = z$. In fact for any integers $x, y, z \in \text{Class } k$, $k = 2, 3, \dots, n$, we have

$$x^y \geq (n^{(k-1)!} + 1)^k > n^{k!} \geq z.$$

Similarly, Class 1 also contains no integers x, y, z with $x^y = z$.

This completes the proof of the theorem.

Reference

[1] F. Smarandache, Only Problems, Not Solutions, Xiquan Publishing House, Chicago, 1993.

[2] Liu Hongyan and Zhang Wenpeng. A note on the 57-th Smarandache's problem. Smarandache Notions Journal **14** (2004), 164-165.